

INFLUENCE OF MEAN STRESS AND WELD LINES ON THE FATIGUE BEHAVIOUR OF SHORT FIBRE REINFORCED POLYAMIDE

Andreas Primetzhofer¹, Andreas Mösenbacher¹ and Gerald Pinter²

¹Department of Product Engineering, Montanuniversitaet Leoben
Franz-Josef-Strasse 18, 8700 Leoben, Austria

Email: andreas.primetzhofer@unileoben.ac.at, web page: <http://amb.unileoben.ac.at/>

²Department of Polymer Engineering and Science, Montanuniversitaet Leoben
Otto Gloeckel-Strasse 2, 8700 Leoben, Austria

Email: gerald.pinter@unileoben.ac.at, web page: <http://www.kunststofftechnik.at/>

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ABSTRACT

In the present work, the influences of mean stress and weld lines on fatigue behaviour of an injection moulded 50 wt% short glass fibre reinforced (sgfr) partial aromatic polyamide were investigated. The influence of mean stress can be considered by the Haigh diagram. The shape of this diagram for sgfr thermoplastics is derived by cyclic, quasi static and creep tests. For these tests, notched and unnotched specimens, which were processed by injection moulding, were used. At first, the material limits were determined with quasi static tests. Since plastics tend to creep under static loads, creep tests were additionally performed to investigate the reduction of sustainable mean stress. Cyclic tests have been made at different stress ratios ranging from $R = 10$ to $R = 0.8$. Finally, for the characterization of the influence of weld lines, specimens were tested perpendicular to the weld line at several stress ratios.

The results show that stress ratio and the related mean stress have a wide influence on the life time of parts made of sgfr plastics. Caused by mean stress redistribution in notched specimens as well as in notched specimens with weld line (labelled as EMS-specimen), the drop-off in fatigue strength at high mean stress levels is lower than for unnotched specimens. This fact has to be considered in a closed simulation chain for example by the stress redistribution according to Neuber's rule. In general, weld lines causes a significant reduction of the fatigue strength compared to the unaffected material.

An improved assessment of mean stress influence by the local stress approach is expected by the proposed Haigh diagram for sgfr PA6T/6I - GF50.

1 INTRODUCTION

For many applications cyclic loads are superimposed by static loads like the weight or preloads caused by clamping conditions. These static loads have a great influence on the fatigue life time of short fibre reinforced polymers. For metals the effect of mean stresses is well known and usually represented in the Haigh diagram, shown in Figure 1, in which the endurable amplitude is plotted as a function of the mean stress. [1] The R-value is defined as the ratio between minimum and maximum stress in a fatigue cycle.

$$R = \frac{S_{a,\min}}{S_{a,\max}} \quad (1)$$

Established approaches are given by the Goodman or the Gerber equations. Another commonly used description of mean stress influence is given by the FKM-guidance. The design of metal components often follows the FKM – guideline where the Haigh diagram is split into four sections according to four mean stress sensibilities M . The sensitivity is described as follows. [2]

$$M = \frac{S_a(R = -1) - S_a(R = 0)}{S_m(R = 0)} = \frac{S_a(R = -1)}{S_a(R = 0)} - 1 \quad (2)$$

In general, the Haigh diagram is limited by the ultimate strength of the material because the upper stress cannot exceed this limit independently from the R -value. Therefore this limitation is represented by a 45° tilted line. Since parts are used over long times especially for thermoplastic materials, it is more expediently to cover this quasi static limit with respect to the influence of time. Therefore creep tests were performed.

Figure 1: Influence of mean stress according to Goodman, Gerber and FKM-guidance [1]

In an injection moulding process weld lines occur whenever two or more fronts of molten material meet. This is the case when the material flow is split by a mould core or different gates are used to fill the cavity. Weld lines also be caused by a partial gap in flow velocity due to varying wall thickness. Based on their formation, two types of weld lines have to be distinguished. Tham Nguyen-Chung [3] has reported the formation of weld lines. On the one hand two melt flows head-on frontally and stay at the meeting point (Type 1). On the other hand the two melt flows meet laterally and keep on flowing as a combined weld line (Type 2). At the flow front the orientation of added fibres is unfavourable and therefore the mechanical properties of weld lines are low. They range around the mechanical properties of unreinforced matrix material or even below.

This article describes the influence of mean stress and weld lines on the fatigue behaviour of a short fibre reinforced partial aromatic polyamide containing 50 wt% glass fibres. Two types of injection moulded specimen were tested under static as well as cyclic loading. The cyclic tests were performed at different R – values.

2 EXPERIMENTAL WORK

2.1 Material and Specimen

The investigated material is a short fibre reinforced partial aromatic polyamide containing 50 wt% glass fibres (PA6T/6I – GF50).

For the tests two types of specimen were used. First specimen type is a “standardized testing specimen” (Type 1A) according to test standard DIN EN ISO 527-2 with a cross-section of 10 x 4 mm. Second specimen is a cross shaped specimen developed by EMS and is called EMS-specimen hereinafter. [4] The exact dimensions and geometry are confidential and cannot be shown here. EMS-specimen can be tested longitudinal and transversal to the flow direction without an influence of machining. Due to the geometry a stress concentration factor has to be considered. Since the EMS-

specimen can be tested transversal to the flow direction, a weld line according to Type 2 can be realized by a pin, inserted in the die during the moulding process. To test the fatigue behaviour of the weld line the specimen is tested perpendicular to the flow direction.

2.2 Cyclic tests

Cyclic test with standardized specimens were carried out on an electro mechanic all-round (tensile/compression and torsional) test machine BOSE ElectroForce 3550[®]. The machine was equipped with a combined 15 kN / 150 Nm load cell. Cyclic test with the EMS-specimen were performed at a servo hydraulic test machine MTS 810[®]. All fatigue tests were performed at 23°C and 50% relative humidity. In former tests the hysterical heating because of high test frequencies were examined. As a result of these tests a frequency of 10 Hz was chosen. [5] The temperature at the surface was monitored with an infrared or a contact thermometer to ensure that the rise of temperature is less than 5°C during the tests. Three stress levels were defined to achieve a range of fatigue cycles to failure from $N = 10^4$ to $N = 10^6$. A sinusoidal load function with constant amplitude is used to run the tests under load control. The *R*-Values for the cyclic tests were $R = -1$, 0.1 and 0.8 complemented by data from [4] at $R = 10$. To get the nominal stress the force is divided by the net cross-section. The abort criterion are the total burst fracture or exceeding the maximum of fatigue cycles $N = 10^7$. The nominal stress amplitude was plotted over fatigue cycles to failure in a double logarithmic graph to generate Woehler-curves. At each stress level at least three specimens were tested. Estimation of S/N-curves is done according to ASTM E 739-91.[6]

2.3 Constant loading tests

To investigate the creep strength of the material, creep tests were performed with standardized specimen at several load levels. To measure the strain, the creep test rig is equipped with an extensometer. The constant load is provided by weights and upset to the specimen over a lever beam. All creep tests were performed at 23°C and a relative humidity of 50%. Temperature was monitored by a contact thermometer during test. The test was aborted by total fracture of the specimen. Stress levels were defined so that the time to failure correlates with the time to failure in a cyclic test. The nominal stress was plotted over time to failure in a double logarithmic graph.

3 RESULT EVALUATION

3.1 Static and fatigue tests on standardized specimen

In Figure 2 the fatigue S/N-curves generated with the standardized specimen is shown under pure tension at two stress ratios ($R = 0.1$ and $R = 0.8$). Test results show that the stress ratio influences the slope of the S/N-curves as well as the fatigue limit.

Figure 2: S/N-curve S_a over N for standardized specimen

During fatigue test under different stress ratios a constant mean stress acts on the specimen and therefore an increase of strain is observed. This behaviour is typically for composite materials with visco-elastic matrix like polyamide. Bernasconi and Mallick have shown this behaviour for sgfr polyamide-6 [7] and polyamide 6,6 [8]. Since polyamides tend to creep under room temperature creep tests were performed at several stress levels. Figure 3 show the stress in the net cross section plotted over the time to rupture. Since the fatigue tests were performed at a frequency of $f = 10$ Hz, a time of 1 s in the creep test represents 10 cycles in an S/N-curve. This plot shows a relation very similar to that of the S/N-curve and therefore the slope was being calculated the same way. [6] The relative fatigue limits S_f at $N = 10^6$ and the slope k are listed in Table 1.

R	Normalized Fatigue limit [-]	Slope k [-]
0.1	0.16	10.2
0.8	0.07	26.6

Table 1: Relative values of fatigue limit at $N = 10^6$ and slope k of standardized specimen

Figure 3: Creep-curve S_{net} over t for standardized specimen

3.2 Notched EMS-specimen

The influence of mean stress and weld line is shown in Figure 4 in a double logarithmic graph. Similar to the results of standardized specimen the notched EMS-specimen also show an influence of the stress ratio on the slope of the S/N-curves as well as on the fatigue limit. With an increasing stress ratio the slope of the S/N-curves increases. Related to respective quasistatic tensile strength the Woehler-curves are congruent for each R-value. The relative fatigue limits S_f at $N = 10^6$ and the slope k are listed in Table 2.

Fibre orientation	R	Normalized Fatigue limit [-]	Slope k [-]
longitudinal	0.1	0.14	8.1
longitudinal	0.8	0.069	24.0
with weld line	0.1	0.13	7.5
with weld line	0.8	0.073	20.6

Table 2: Relative values of fatigue limit at $N = 10^6$ and slope k of EMS-specimen

Figure 4: S/N curve for EMS-specimen under various stress ratios tested longitudinal and with weld line

3.3 Influence of Mean Stress and weld lines

To describe the influence of mean stress the Haigh diagram is used. The fatigue strength for each test series at $N = 10^6$ is plotted along respective line with constant stress ratio (dotted lines in Figure 5). Compared to the unnotched standardized specimen the EMS-specimen show a lower nominal fatigue limit at both stress ratios. A weld line causes, as expected, a strong decrease of the fatigue limit to about 30 % of the longitudinal oriented specimen. Both types of notched specimen (EMS-specimen with and without weld line) show a lower mean stress sensibility M than the unnotched standardized specimen expressed by a lower slope of the line between the fatigue limit at $R = 0.1$ and $R = 0.8$. The Haigh diagram normally is bounded by the ultimate strength R_m of the material (dashed line in Figure 5) since the upper stress S_{max} cannot exceed this material limit. This limit is reduced by the effects of creep for a longer service time. For polymer material the maximum mean stress is limited by creep strength. This fact has to be taken into account and therefore the maximum endurable mean stress is limited by the creep strength assignable to the test in time to reach for example $N = 10^6$ cycles to failure (dot dashed line in Figure 5).

Figure 5: Haigh diagram at $N = 10^6$ for standardized specimen; EMS-specimen longitudinal and EMS-specimen with weld line

For comparison of the notched EMS-specimen to the unnotched standardized specimen the effect of notch support has to be taken into account. Also the different fibre orientation of specimen has to be considered. Based on the material behaviour (Young's modulus, ultimate strength, yield strength and fatigue data) of two known orientation conditions (transversal and longitudinal) the influence of fibre orientation can be considered by linear interpolation in a semi logarithmic scale. [9] Since the direction of fibres and the degree of orientation are known from a moulding simulation, all material parameters could be convert to the fibre orientation of each type of specimen.

As known from metal materials, based on maximum notch stress, notched specimen show a longer fatigue life. As a result of viscoelastic-plastic material behaviour the notch support effect is more pronounced for thermoplastic materials. To characterize the notch support effect based on finite element results, the relative stress gradient is established as a reference value for the sharpness of the notch. In this work notch support is described by equation (3) following [10, 11]. The notch sensitivity factor n_χ depending on the relative stress gradient χ' at a reference gradient $\chi'_{ref} = 1$ is given in (3). The factor f represents the ratio between the fatigue limit of the model at a reference gradient $\chi'_{ref} = 1$ and at pure tension.

$$n_\chi = 1 + (f - 1) \cdot \chi'^{K_D} \quad (3)$$

If the explained models for fibre orientation and notch support are available, the local fatigue behaviour of notched specimen can compared with unnotched one by recalculation. Figure 6 exhibits the recalculated results of the notched EMS-specimen compared to the unnotched standardized specimen.

Figure 6: Haigh diagram at $N = 10^6$ for standardized specimen and converted data for EMS-specimen longitudinal

Especially at high mean stress the notched specimen seems to show higher endurable stress amplitude and therefore a higher mean stress for comparable stress ratio. In real quite likely mean stresses at the notch root are reduced and rearranged by creep and plasticisation effects of the material. This fact has to be considered for a closed simulation chain for instance by mean stress redistribution according to Neuber's rule. [12] Especially if the stresses in a closed simulation chain are calculated with a linear elastic material model, the plasticisation and mean stress redistribution has to be covered in this way.

As shown in Figure 5 notched specimen with weld line leads to a lower mean stress sensibility M than unnotched standardized and notched EMS-specimen (longitudinal). Since the material behaviour of weld lines is dominated by viscoelastic-plastic properties of the matrix, the presumption of stress redistribution due to viscoelastic-plastic is strengthened.

In Figure 7 a proposal based on the test data at $N = 10^6$ for the mean stress influence of the investigated material is given. Therefore three sections with different mean stress sensibilities are defined. At pure alternating tension/compression ($R = -1$) the bearable stress amplitude is around 26 % of the ultimate strength of the material. The value of the mean stress sensibility M , defined between $R = -1$ and $R = 0.1$, is $M = 0.5$. Because of creep effects the maximum endurable mean stress is reduced to 72 % of the ultimate strength. This point is connected to the tensile strength at $R = -1$ until to the stress ratio $R = 0.8$. Between $R = 0.1$ and $R = 0.8$ the resulting points of mean stress sensibility and creep rupture are connected. For the compression dominated part of the graph ($-1 < R < 0$), M is reduced by a factor of 2.0.

Figure 7: Proposal for consideration of the influence of mean stress at $N = 10^6$

4 SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

Fatigue tests under pure tension were performed at different stress ratios with unnotched, notched and notched specimen with weld line. The test results show that the fatigue behaviour of short fibre reinforced polyamide is strongly influenced by mean stress. For all types of specimen the fatigue strength decreases with increasing mean stress. Fatigue strength of notched specimen with weld line is reduced to about one third compared to notched specimen without weld lines. Creep tests were performed to investigate the static material limit for longer service times in the Haigh diagram. Due to creep the mechanical bound is reduced to about 72% of the ultimate strength for $N = 10^6$ cycles to failure. Based on the test results, a proposal for the mean stress influence is given. Compared to notched specimen, unnotched specimen shows a lower fatigue limit at higher mean stress. This is justified by stress redistribution and has to be covered in a closed simulation chain for example by Neuber's rule.

To investigate the influence of viscoelastic-plastic material behaviour of short fibre reinforced polyamide on fatigue, additional tests focusing on the cyclic stress/strain behaviour of the material should be performed.

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